

OPEN ACCESS

EDITED AND REVIEWED BY
Ramani Ramchandran,
Medical College of Wisconsin,
United States

*CORRESPONDENCE
Benjamin Gantenbein,
✉ Benjamin.Gantenbein@unibe.ch

RECEIVED 29 March 2023
ACCEPTED 14 April 2023
PUBLISHED 20 April 2023

CITATION
Gantenbein B, Sun Z, Liu Z and
Samartzis D (2023), Editorial:
Immunological imbalance: What is its role
in intervertebral disc degeneration?
Front. Cell Dev. Biol. 11:1196377.
doi: 10.3389/fcell.2023.1196377

COPYRIGHT
© 2023 Gantenbein, Sun, Liu and
Samartzis. This is an open-access article
distributed under the terms of the
[Creative Commons Attribution License
\(CC BY\)](#). The use, distribution or
reproduction in other forums is
permitted, provided the original author(s)
and the copyright owner(s) are credited
and that the original publication in this
journal is cited, in accordance with
accepted academic practice. No use,
distribution or reproduction is permitted
which does not comply with these terms.

Editorial: Immunological imbalance: What is its role in intervertebral disc degeneration?

Benjamin Gantenbein^{1,2*}, Zhen Sun³, Zhongyang Liu⁴ and
Dino Samartzis⁵

¹Tissue Engineering for Orthopaedics and Mechanobiology, Bone and Joint Program, Department for BioMedical Research (DBMR) of the Medical Faculty, University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland, ²Department of Orthopaedic Surgery and Traumatology, Inselspital, Bern University Hospital, Medical Faculty, University of Bern, Bern, Switzerland, ³Department of Orthopaedics, Xijing Hospital, Fourth Military Medical University, Xi'an, China, ⁴Department of Orthopaedics, Chinese PLA General Hospital, Beijing, China, ⁵Rush Medical College, Rush University, Chicago, IL, United States

KEYWORDS

miRNA, single-cell RNA-seq, intervertebral disc, IL17, immune cells, macrophages, low back pain

Editorial on the research topic
[Immunological imbalance: What is its role in intervertebral disc degeneration?](#)

1 Introduction

Low back pain (LBP) is a major cause of disability worldwide (GBD, 2017 Disease and Injury Incidence and Prevalence Collaborators, 2018) and belongs to the most urgent priorities to identify novel therapies, especially for the elderly (Teichtahl et al., 2015; Chen et al., 2020; Lee et al., 2021). Global health costs are generally rising but in the field of orthopedics and mostly for spine, the costs are exploding in recent years compared to other diseases (Wieser et al., 2011; Martin et al., 2019). Surgical options to treat LBP efficiently are very limited; clinical outcome is often non-satisfactory for the patients with very high re-operation rates (Nachemson et al., 1996; Knezevic et al., 2021). In clinical daily life most of the time “discectomy” is practiced, which is the surgical removal of the painful intervertebral disc (IVD) with a subsequent insertion of a metallic cage as a placeholder and pedicle screws and rods to achieve a so-called spinal fusion (Martin et al., 2019). LBP has many facets but in the cases where the pain is caused from degenerated IVDs, it is usually caused from a reduction in disc height, which then leads to continuous irritation of the nerves. Traditionally, there were mainly two hypotheses formulated that IVDs degenerate early apart from genetic pre-disposal. The first one is the so-called “limited nutrition hypothesis” formulated by Jill Urban and colleagues (Urban et al., 2004; Huang et al., 2014). The second hypothesis was formulated by Adams and Roughley (2006) that claims that IVDs can degenerate because of mechanical overloading. These two hypotheses do not exclude themselves. Possibly in reality, it is often a combination of both, mechanical overloading and limited nutrition (Zengerle et al., 2021). Of course, it is said from these perspectives that the immune-system does not play a major role for IVD degeneration as it was always claimed that the lack of blood vessels in the healthy IVD makes this an “immune-privileged” environment (Bermudez-Lekerika et al.). However, there is increasing evidence that the immune-system might also play a central role in

the onset of IVD-induced LBP (Lambrechts et al., 2023). Also the importance of bacteria entering the IVD through the endplates or through other routes, e.g., through the outer annulus fibrosus (AF), were recently discussed (Dudli et al., 2018; Bermudez-Lekerika et al.; Ye et al., 2022). It has been hypothesized that bacterial infection might be a possible cause for so-called type 1 Modic changes as revealed by magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) (Modic et al., 1988; Dudli et al., 2018).

This Research Topic entitled “Immunological Imbalance: What is its Role in Intervertebral Disc (IVD) Degeneration?” focuses on current insights of possible causes for IVD degeneration in the context of the neglected role of the microbiome (Steves et al., 2016; Jackson et al., 2018; Rajasekaran et al., 2020). The Research Topic comprises a total of five publications, whereas three of these are reviews articles (Li et al.; Bermudez-Lekerika et al.; Suyama et al.) and two of them are original research articles (Song et al.; Li et al.).

The two recent original research articles use large -omics molecular data to address answers for clinical problems. The team by Song et al. focuses on the importance of Hsa_circ_000065 in ankylosing spondylitis (AS) and its importance for the intervertebral disc (IVD). Micro RNA (miRNA) research belongs into the most important and fast growing research areas of regenerative medicine and tissue engineering. The field of miRNA is surely one of the most promising research areas for the identification of future therapies (Guo et al., 2023).

The second original research article in this Research Topic then by Li et al. published novel insights on the roles of blood lipid-metabolism genes in immune infiltration using transcriptomics data approach could promote the development of intervertebral disc disease (IDD). Both articles use latest state-of-the-art bioinformatics and also provide extensive data on these very important questions.

2 Three review articles in the research topic on “hot research topic”

On the side of the review in this Research Topic, we are happy to have received this very detailed study by Li et al. on the description of extracellular vesicles (EVs) and their potential role for IVD repair. This study can be recommended for researchers interested in the fast growing field along with another important review that were recently published on EVs and the field of IVD repair and regeneration (Li et al.; Tilotta et al., 2021).

Furthermore, IL17 has been mainly overlooked in the literature, especially with a special focus on the IVD is then presented by Suyama et al. In this very nice overview review article the reader learns how IL17 might be involved in the autoimmune disease progression in IVD herniation and degeneration. There also seems a correlation between the increase of TH17 T-cell population in patients suffering from disc herniation (Suyama et al.).

The final review that is presented in this Research Topic is written by members of the recently launched “disc4all” consortium. This cross-disciplinary research project, that is funded by a Marie Skłodowska Curie International Training Network (ITN), is at the interface of translational research and consists of computer modelers, biomedical engineers, biologists and clinicians to identify common patterns and strategies that cause the disease in the population. In this review a special focus was done on recent advances in finite element modeling but also in the

understanding how immune cells might affect the onset and progress of IVD degeneration (Bermudez-Lekerika et al.).

3 Conclusion

This Research Topic is an important hallmark especially highlighting the role of the immune system for IVD research with contributors from wide fields of scientific backgrounds. In the future more articles on translational research on common disabilities that might interfere with IVD-induced low back pain such as diabetes and direct and indirect influence of microbiomes are needed. Furthermore, we will need more studies using -omics approach in the fields of miRNA, transcriptomics, and then meta-studies comparing multiple -omics data with the assistance of artificial intelligence (AI) to help interpretation of the data. Furthermore, EVs might be more applicable as a therapy than injection of cells as a therapy (Li et al.). Overall, we may conclude that this Research Topic is a nice small overview of up-to-date research in the emergent field to identify new cures for IVD-related LBP research.

Author contributions

All authors listed have made a substantial, direct, and intellectual contribution to the work and approved it for publication.

Funding

BG wishes to acknowledge his funding sources, namely, the Marie Skłodowska Curie International Training Network (ITN) “disc4all” (<https://disc4all.upf.edu>, accessed on 22 March 2023) grant agreement #955735 (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/955735>, accessed on 22 March 2023), the iPSpine project (<https://ipspine.eu>, accessed 17 April 2023) under the grant agreement #825925 (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/825925>, accessed 17 April 2023) and the Swiss National Science Foundation projects #310030E_192674/1 (<https://data.snf.ch/grants/grant/192674>, accessed on 23 March 2023) and project #40B2-0_211510/1 (<https://data.snf.ch/grants/grant/211510>, accessed on 23 March 2023). ZS acknowledges the National Natural Science Foundation of China (grant #82002348).

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Publisher’s note

All claims expressed in this article are solely those of the authors and do not necessarily represent those of their affiliated organizations, or those of the publisher, the editors and the reviewers. Any product that may be evaluated in this article, or claim that may be made by its manufacturer, is not guaranteed or endorsed by the publisher.

References

- Adams, M. A., and Roughley, P. J. (2006). What is intervertebral disc degeneration, and what causes it? *Spine*, 31, 2151–2161. doi:10.1097/01.brs.0000231761.73859.2c
- Chen, S., Luo, M., Kou, H., Shang, G., Ji, Y., and Liu, H. (2020). A review of gene therapy delivery systems for intervertebral disc degeneration. *Curr. Pharm. Biotechnol.* 21, 194–205. doi:10.2174/1389201020666191024171618
- Dudli, S., Miller, S., Demir-Deviren, S., and Lotz, J. C. (2018). Inflammatory response of disc cells against *Propionibacterium acnes* depends on the presence of lumbar Modic changes. *Eur. Spine. J.* 27, 1013–1020. doi:10.1007/s00586-017-5291-4
- Gbd 2017 Disease and Injury Incidence and Prevalence Collaborators (2018). Global, regional, and national incidence, prevalence, and years lived with disability for 354 diseases and injuries for 195 countries and territories, 1990–2017: A systematic analysis for the global burden of disease study 2017. *Lancet*, 392, 1789–1858. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(18)32279-7
- Guo, C., Chen, Y., Wang, Y., and Hao, Y. (2023). Regulatory roles of noncoding RNAs in intervertebral disc degeneration as potential therapeutic targets (Review). *Exp. Ther. Med.* 25, 44. doi:10.3892/etm.2022.11743
- Huang, Y. C., Urban, J. P., and Luk, K. D. (2014). Intervertebral disc regeneration: Do nutrients lead the way? *Nat. Rev. Rheumatol.* 10, 561–566. doi:10.1038/nrrheum.2014.91
- Jackson, M. A., Verdi, S., Maxam, M. E., Shin, C. M., Zierer, J., Bowyer, R. C. E., et al. (2018). Gut microbiota associations with common diseases and prescription medications in a population-based cohort. *Nat. Commun.* 9, 2655. doi:10.1038/s41467-018-05184-7
- Knezevic, N. N., Candido, K. D., Vlaeyen, J. W. S., Van Zundert, J., and Cohen, S. P. (2021). Low back pain. *Lancet* 398, 78–92. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(21)00733-9
- Lambrechts, M. J., Pitchford, C., Hogan, D., Li, J., Fogarty, C., Rawat, S., et al. (2023). Lumbar spine intervertebral disc desiccation is associated with medical comorbidities linked to systemic inflammation. *Arch. Orthop. Trauma. Surg.* 143, 1143–1153. doi:10.1007/s00402-021-04194-3
- Lee, C. K., Heo, D. H., Chung, H., Roh, E. J., Darai, A., Kyung, J. W., et al. (2021). Advances in tissue engineering for disc repair. *Appl. Sci.* 11, 1919. doi:10.3390/app11041919
- Martin, B. I., Mirza, S. K., Spina, N., Spiker, W. R., Lawrence, B., and Brodke, D. S. (2019). Trends in lumbar fusion procedure rates and associated hospital costs for degenerative spinal diseases in the United States, 2004 to 2015. *Spine* 44, 369–376. doi:10.1097/brs.0000000000002822
- Modic, M. T., Steinberg, P. M., Ross, J. S., Masaryk, T. J., and Carter, J. R. (1988). Degenerative disk disease: Assessment of changes in vertebral body marrow with MR imaging. *Radiology* 166, 193–199. doi:10.1148/radiology.166.1.3336678
- Nachemson, A., Zdeblick, T. A., and O'Brien, J. P. (1996). Lumbar disc disease with discogenic pain. What surgical treatment is most effective? *Spine* 21, 1835–1838. doi:10.1097/00007632-199608010-00023
- Rajasekaran, S., Soundararajan, D. C. R., Tangavel, C., Muthurajan, R., Sri Vijay Anand, K. S., Matchado, M. S., et al. (2020). Human intervertebral discs harbour a unique microbiome and dysbiosis determines health and disease. *Eur. Spine. J.* 29, 1621–1640. doi:10.1007/s00586-020-06446-z
- Steves, C. J., Bird, S., Williams, F. M., and Spector, T. D. (2016). The microbiome and musculoskeletal conditions of aging: A review of evidence for impact and potential therapeutics. *J. Bone. Min. Res.* 31, 261–269. doi:10.1002/jbmr.2765
- Teichtahl, A. J., Urquhart, D. M., Wang, Y., Wluka, A. E., O'Sullivan, R., Jones, G., et al. (2015). Physical inactivity is associated with narrower lumbar intervertebral discs, high fat content of paraspinal muscles and low back pain and disability. *Arthritis. Res. Ther.* 17, 114. doi:10.1186/s13075-015-0629-y
- Tilotta, V., Vadalà, G., Ambrosio, L., Russo, F., Cicioni, C., Di Giacomo, G., et al. (2021). Mesenchymal stem cell-derived exosomes: The new frontier for the treatment of intervertebral disc degeneration. *Appl. Sci.* 11, 11222. doi:10.3390/app112311222
- Urban, J. P., Smith, S., and Fairbank, J. C. (2004). Nutrition of the intervertebral disc. *Spine* 29, 2700–2709. doi:10.1097/01.brs.0000146499.97948.52
- Wieser, S., Horisberger, B., Schmidhauser, S., Eisenring, C., Brügger, U., Ruckstuhl, A., et al. (2011). Cost of low back pain in Switzerland in 2005. *Eur. J. Health. Econ.* 12, 455–467. doi:10.1007/s10198-010-0258-y
- Ye, F., Lyu, F. J., Wang, H., and Zheng, Z. (2022). The involvement of immune system in intervertebral disc herniation and degeneration. *JOR Spine* 5, e1196. doi:10.1002/jsp2.1196
- Zengerle, L., Debout, E., Kluger, B., Zöllner, L., and Wilke, H.-J. (2021). *In vitro* model for lumbar disc herniation to investigate regenerative tissue repair approaches. *Appl. Sci.* 11, 2847. doi:10.3390/app11062847